

Quantum Bound State Wavefunction and Dynamics

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In classical physics, a potential $V(x)$ acts on a particle at a location x regardless of its velocity which is taken to be constant within dx (even though the particle accelerates). Thus writing potential energy $V(x)$ at a given x is like taking a snapshot of the particle when it is at x . The snapshot is static and does not indicate the dynamics of the problem as the particle may be moving either to the right or left, which is irrelevant in terms of the exact potential energy and even kinetic energy at point x .

A quantum particle moving with constant velocity is described by a two-dimensional dynamic probability $\exp(ipx)$, with $\cos(px)$ representing a static density and $\sin(px)$ a time-shifted density to capture one directional motion such that $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)=1$, we argue. $V(x)$, however, only acts on the static density (linked to $\cos(px)$ and not $\sin(px)$). Thus it seems that bound state quantum mechanics needs to remove the dynamic pieces of free particle wavefunctions $\exp(ipx)$ through interference. One might argue that for wavelengths of the order of the system length one does not know if one has $\exp(ipx)$ or $\exp(-ipx)$ at an x point, but for high energy levels, wavelengths become small with respect to the system length and yet interference is still present. Thus it seems that for the calculation of energy one requires a static average snapshot of the bound particle. Physically, we argue that the dynamic piece is still present i.e.. if one knocks out a bound particle and it is found in the p momentum state, it is represented by $\exp(ipx)$. Thus the purpose of the bound state wavefunction is to facilitate the calculation of average energy which is associated with a static snapshot type of density and not necessarily represent all of the dynamical information in the system i.e. the two dimensionality of each $\exp(ipx)$. As a result, the bound wavefunction does not show motion to the right and then to the left in the high energy limit.

Classical Mechanics and a Potential $V(x)$

In classical mechanics, a particle at point x , for which a potential $V(x)$ exists, has a potential energy of $V(x)$ regardless of its velocity. Furthermore, the velocity is taken to be constant to first order in a tiny dx , even though the particle is accelerating. Thus the particle has kinetic energy $pp/2m$ at x and $pp/2m + V(x)$ is a constant. Due to time reversal symmetry, one may reverse the direction of the particle and so even if it moves in one direction, it may be thought of as being part of a bound state i.e. its velocity will ultimately become 0 at some x and it will change direction in many $V(x)$ examples, e.g. an oscillator $V(x)=.5kxx$ etc.

Quantum Free Particle

A quantum free particle is not defined at a point even though it has a density of $1/\sqrt{L}$ where L is length. In particular, it is represented by a two dimensional wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ which we argue contains two distributions, $\cos(px)$ a static distribution at time t and $\sin(px)$ a shifted distribution at later time to indicate the direction of motion such that $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = 1$ i.e. all x points are treated the same in the density scenario. $\cos(px)$, however, indicates that a

static snapshot of the free particle has a distribution in x including probabilities of 0. Given that the particle is dynamic, one needs both $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ in two dimensions to properly describe it. Its kinetic energy, however, is $p^2/2m$ at any x point and its potential energy $V(x)$ seems to act only on the static distribution in a bound i.e. classical scenario. Thus $V(x)$ should only act on $\cos(px)$ even though the full dynamic probability is $\exp(ipx)$.

Quantum Bound State

Given that any free particle i.e. constant velocity is associated with a fixed length \hbar/p , one cannot consider the free particle to be at one x point when it has a certain p value as in the classical scenario. Only the $\cos(px)$ static piece of the wavefunction, however, is required for a calculation of potential energy. In fact, the time independent Schrodinger equation may be multiplied by $W(x)$, the bound wavefunction, so one explicitly sees the “snapshot” spatial density $W(x)W(x)$;

$$W_n(x) \left(-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW_n}{dx} \right) + V(x) W_n(x)W_n(x) = E_n W_n(x)W_n(x) \quad ((1))$$

Thus the wavefunction itself and not the density appears in the time-independent Schrodinger equation through the kinetic energy term as $\cos(px)$ is an eigenfunction of $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx}$. In order to remove the $i \sin(px)$ portions of the wavefunction $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ ((2)) with $a(p)=a(-p)$, one uses interference. One is left with a static snapshot of $2a(p)\cos(px)$ for each p . $\cos(px)$ does not indicate in which direction the particle moves, but if a particle were to be knocked out of the bound state and found to be in a state with momentum p , it would have a probability of $a(p)a(p)$ to be in this p state and would be represented by $\exp(ipx)$ and not $\cos(px)$. Thus we argue that interference of $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ in the wavefunction facilitates the calculation of potential energy by removing the dynamical probability portions.

The next issue, however, is the fact that $\cos(px)$ and not $\cos(px)\cos(px)$ is used in calculating kinetic energy in ((1)) and $W_n(x)W_n(x)$ allows for interference. To try to describe this, we argue that given different $\cos(px)$'s, which represent a repeated x probability distribution, one tries to replace a single $\cos(px)$ with an averaged repeated probability distribution which has different peak heights and widths, with $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W$ still representing kinetic energy as it did for a free particle $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \cos(px) / \cos(px)$. $V(x)$ then acts on the average $W_n(x)$, which has dynamical probability removed.

If one considers low energies and wavelength \hbar/p of the order of the system length, then it makes sense to have $\exp(ipx)$ mixed with $\exp(-ipx)$ as $\cos(px)$ of each overlap as one has a probability distribution in x . In other words, not only does one not know at what specific x a free particle with p is found, but one doesn't know if it is already moving backwards. As energy levels increase, however, wavelengths become small with respect to the system length and this argument no longer holds, but interference still applies because one only wishes to have the static snapshot of the system and this is associated with a real wavefunction, even though physically a particle with p is represented by the two dimensional $\exp(ipx)$. This two dimensional probability, however, may represent the particle at any x point.

As a result, we argue that a bound wavefunction is real in order to facilitate the calculation of potential energy which is based on a “snapshot” static density and not the full dynamic picture.

The goal of the time-independent Schrodinger equation is to obtain a single energy value corresponding to its energy eigenfunction which is associated with a static snapshot density. In classical physics this is fine as a particle is found at x , but in quantum mechanics a free particle is not at x and is represented by two distributions $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$.

Thus the bound single particle wavefunction does not show the particle moving in one direction or the other even for high energy levels as classical motion dictates. As a result, we argue that the bound state wavefunction cannot contain all of the information of the problem and is used to yield energy and a static density which does not depend on which direction the particle moves.

Time-Dependent Schrodinger Equation

It is possible to include the full dynamics in the time-dependent Schrodinger equation. In such a case, the wavefunction is complex and may be written as:

$$W(x,t) = \sum_n a_n(t) W_n(x) \quad ((3))$$

Here $W_n(x)$ is an energy eigenfunction for which the dynamic portions of $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ have canceled. The particle is present and moving in a potential, but no longer has a constant energy at each x as in the classical picture. Given that potential energy $V(x)$ is measured acting on a static snapshot spatial density, $W_n(x)$ yields a picture in which this classical type behaviour is again present except for the fact that $W_n(x)$'s interfere and so one does not know which E energy one has.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a quantum free particle, unlike a classical particle, is described by a two dimensional dynamic probability $\exp(ipx)$. $\cos(px)$ is the static part of the probability, we argue, but does not describe the direction of motion which must be provided by the two pieces. In terms of potential energy, however, classically one only needs the static snapshot density, not a dynamic one. $V(x)$ does not depend on the velocity of the particle or its momentum p . Thus for a bound state problem, the second dimension of probability may be removed through interference even though physically a particle with a momentum p (which may be knocked out of the bound state) is represented by $\exp(ipx)$. Thus interference facilitates the calculation of potential energy by keeping only the static piece of probability for all energy levels, but loses the directional pieces of the dynamics i.e. direction of motion which is not needed for the calculation of energy. Interference does more than remove the complex pieces of probability, it creates a new peak/trough structure to replace the $\cos(px)$ form of a free particle. Thus we argue that a bound state wavefunction is linked with a snapshot density, but this snapshot static density does not contain the full dynamics of the problem. It is useful to describe the potential energy snapshot i.e. $W (-\hbar^2/2m d^2/dx^2 + V(x))W = E W$. The point we make is that a moving quantum particle is more than its static probability portion and so even the average with interference is somewhat static. This feature also shows why high energy levels still use

interference and do not indicate the direction in which a particle moves (which is not necessary for an energy description with no time present), but is incomplete information.